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COURSE OF SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS DEPENDING ON CLIMATE AND GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

Explicit clinical symptoms of heart failure in systemic lupus erythematosus are found in 51.4% of patients. Lung damage in SLE is often indicated as an infectious complication due to immunosuppressive therapy, especially long-term treatment with large doses of corticosteroids, rather than as a result of the severe course of the disease itself. Frequent symptoms of damage to the nervous system were sleep disturbances, which manifested itself in the form of lengthening the time of falling asleep, reducing the depth and duration of night sleep, rapid awakening and daytime sleepiness. Uncontrolled activity of the lupus process caused the appearance of severe manifestations, such as pneumonitis, pleurisy and pericarditis (serosites and polyserosites) and vasculitis.

Keywords: Systemic lupus erythematosus, myocarditis, endocarditis, pneumonitis, climate.

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ТЕЧЕНИЕ СИСТЕМНОЙ КРАСНОЙ ВОЛЧАНКИ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ КЛИМАТО-ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Явные клинические симптомы поражения сердца при системной красной волчанке обнаруживаются у 51,4% больных. Поражение легких при СКВ часто указывается, как инфекционное осложнение вследствие иммуносупрессивной терапии, особенно длительного лечения большими дозами кортикостероидов, нежели в результате тяжелого течения самого заболевания. Частыми симптомами поражения нервной системы явились нарушение сна, которое проявлялось в виде удлинения продолжительности времени засыпания, уменьшения глубины и длительности ночного сна, быстрого пробуждения и дневной сонливости. Неконтролируемая активность волчаночного процесса явилась причиной появления тяжелых проявлений, таких как пневмонит, плеврит и перикардит (серозиты и полисерозиты) и васкулиты.

Ключевые слова: Системная красная волчанка, миокардит, эндокардит, пневмонит, климат.

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ИҚЛИМ-ГЕОГРАФИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРГА БОҒЛИК БЎЛГАН ТИЗИМЛИ ҚИЗИЛ ЮГУРИК КАСАЛЛИКНИНГ КЕЧИШИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Тизимли қизил югурик билан касалланган беморларнинг 51.4 % да юракнинг зарарланишининг аниқ клиник симптомлари кузатилди. ТҚЮда иммуносупрессив терапия натижасида инфекцион асоратларни кўшилиши, асосан кортикостероидлар билан ўзоқ даволаш ҳамда касалликнинг ўзини оғир кечиши кўп ҳолларда ўпканинг зарарланишига олиб келади. Нерв тизимининг зарарланиши асосий белгиси ўйку бузилиши ҳисобланиб, ўйкунинг чуқурлиги ва давомийлигининг камайиши, тез уйғониш ҳамда кундузги ўйкучанлик билан намоён бўлади. Патогенетик жараёни фаоллигини бошқариб бўлмайдиган сабаблари пневмонит, плеврит ва перикардит (серозит ва полисерозитлар) ва васкулитларнинг оғир кўринишлари ҳисобланади.

Калит сўзлар: Тизимли қизил югурик, миокардит, эндокардит, пневмонит, иқлим.

(Literature review)

Introduction. Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is one of the most severe systemic diseases of connective tissue, more common at the age of 20-40 years, and about 90% of cases are women (1; 2). Over the past decades, there has been an increase in the frequency of SLE (50-250 cases per 100 thousand population), which is referred to the improvement of diagnostic methods, the identification of latent and chronic forms, and in some cases - overdiagnosis. The difficulties of diagnosing systemic lupus erythematosus are due to the fact that often the appearance of detailed clinical signs of the disease is preceded by an asymptomatic period with minimal laboratory manifestations of the disease (7). The diagnostic criteria of the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) (1982, 1997) were developed for epidemiological studies and do not always allow one hundred percent probability to exclude or confirm the diagnosis of SLE, especially in the early stages and atypical variants of the disease (3; 4). When studying the medical documentation of one of the major medical institutions, J. Calyo et al. (5) found that among patients diagnosed with SLE, only two-thirds met the criteria for ACR, whereas about 10% had signs of lupus not in full volume to verify a reliable diagnosis, and 25% showed a pattern of fibromyalgia in combination with positive antinuclear antibodies (AA), while even with long-term observation, there was no evolution of the disease into a reliable SLE. The question of improving the criteria for diagnosing SLE, "chameleon disease," or "the great imitator of diseases" (6) has been repeatedly raised. In 2012, a group of experts from Systemic Lupus International Collaborating Clinics (SLICC) presented the results of a multi-year analysis of a large number of medical histories (about 700 patients) with SLE and proposed modified diagnostic criteria for diagnosis, expanded by the introduction of a number of dermatological, neurological signs with more accurate indicators (6;8).

In this regard, early diagnosis of SLE is of particular relevance, since pathogenetic therapy prescribed in a timely manner (getting into the "window of opportunity") is an important factor in achieving remission of the disease. According to the point of view of a number of authors, the debut of SLE is preceded by a preclinical phase characterized by disorders of immunological tolerance with expression of autoantibodies, signs of immune dysregulation and nonspecific clinical symptoms (fever, weight loss, fatigue, arthralgia, myalgia), which over a short period can potentially transform into an early stage of the disease (7).

Joint involvement is a common symptom of SLE, characterized by moderate pain and inflammatory changes (mainly wrist joints, small joints of the hand and knee), short morning stiffness and the absence of erosive changes on radiographs (9). In the active phase of SLE, patients complain of myalgia, but true myositis is rarely observed. It was found that in patients with SLE with myositis,

the frequency of alopecia, ulcerative stomatitis, erosive arthritis and lung damage is increased and secondary Shogren syndrome and nephritis are rare (10;11).

Skin involvement is the second most common symptom of SLE after joint involvement; occurs in 70-80% of cases and can prevail in the onset of the disease in 23-28% of patients. Dermatological manifestations that are most important: photosensitization, butterfly, discoid rashes and ulcerative stomatitis belong to the criteria for ACR necessary to establish a reliable diagnosis of SLE. In addition, a number of symptoms unconditionally indicate the activity of the process, for example, centrifugal Biett's erythema ("butterfly"), capillarites, enanthema, cheilitis. There is a distinction between so-called lupus-specific and lupus-non-specific skin lesions, and the latter are several times more common in SLE (9; 12). Lupus-specific manifestations include chronic lupus erythematosus (discoid rashes, lupus panniculitis, tumor-like lupus), subacute cutaneous lupus erythematosus (anular-polycyclic type, psoriasiform type, Rowell syndrome) and acute lupus erythematosus (the most typical sign is "butterfly"). Nonspecific skin manifestations include photosensitization, leukocytoclassical and urticarial vasculitis, telangiectasia, reticular livedo, malignant atrophic papulosis (Dego syndrome), Raynaud syndrome. In patients with SLE, sclerodactyly, rheumatoid nodules, calcification, bullous changes, urticaria, papulonodular mucinosis, anetoderma, erythema multiforme and chronic trophic ulcers of the lower extremities can occur. Antiphospholipids (AFS) play a large role in the development of some manifestations (7).

The frequency of pericarditis, according to autopsy and echocardiographic studies, reaches 60-70%, however, clinically obvious pericardial damage occurs in about every 4th patient, accompanied, as a rule, by other signs of lupus activity. Immunological examination shows ASA, antibodies to double-stranded DNA, LE cells, low level of C3- and C4 component of complement. Myocarditis occurs against the background of high activity of arterial hypertension disease and coronary heart disease (CHD), but may also be a consequence of a high cumulative dose of HA or the toxic effect of cyclophosphamide and long-term use of aminoquinoline drugs (11). Liebman-Sachs endocarditis with the presence of aseptic verrucose vegetations on heart valves, papillary muscles or endocardium is considered a characteristic valve lesion for SLE (7; 8). Pleural involvement in the pathological process occurs in 41-56% of SLE patients, more often in men and African Americans.

Data on the specificity of ANA determination in pleural fluid in SLE patients are inconsistent (13;14). Acute lupus pneumonitis occurs in 1-9% of patients with SLE. In the vast majority of cases (90-95%), hemorrhagic pneumonitis is associated with kidney damage, often (13-57%) there is an addition of concomitant viral or bacterial infection, especially in patients receiving cyclophosphamide.

The incidence of gastrointestinal (GI) manifestations varies significantly (from 1 to 30%). The most common (up to 50% of patients) are anorexia, nausea and vomiting, both during exacerbations and against the background of complications of the disease (for example, uremia) and taking drugs. Oral involvement in 13-20% of patients is associated with secondary Sjögren syndrome. Esophagitis in patients with SLE, unlike patients with systemic scleroderma, is extremely rare (less than 3%) and is mainly due to either HA therapy or fungal damage (candidiasis esophagitis) (3). There are manifestations associated with aFL: arterial and venous occlusions, Budd-Chiari syndrome, nodular regenerative hyperplasia. (4;5).

Renal involvement (lupus glomerulonephritis - LGN) is a prognostically unfavorable manifestation of SLE. Clinically significant LGN is observed in 40-60% of patients, but the true incidence of renal pathology is much higher: recent randomized clinical trials have demonstrated histological changes in biopsies in 90% of patients, even without obvious changes in physical examination and urine tests (6).

Neurological symptoms are a serious manifestation in patients with SLE. The frequency of neuropsychiatric disorders, according to different authors, varies from 37 to 95% depending on the choice of diagnostic methods and the nature of the groups studied. CNS lesions are approximately 10 times more common than peripheral nervous system lesions, diffuse lesions are 4 times more common than focal neurological symptoms. In 2000, when studying the spectrum of neuropsychiatric manifestations in 572 patients with SLE, it was found that neurological symptoms in the first 5 years

of the disease were observed in 30% of patients, with headache, anxiety, mood swings, cognitive impairment, seizures, polyneuropathy, psychosis, etc. (12). Psychoses occur in approximately 5% of patients and, along with the active process, can be caused by prolonged administration of high doses of GC, narcotic drugs, schizophrenia and depression (7;8).

A new promising method and a new branch of medicine is the study of the features of diseases depending on the place of residence of patients, the study of climatic rhythms of physiological indicators and taking into account the dynamics of geographical rhythms to clarify the issues of adaptation and treatment. Currently, geographical medicine has numerous experimental and clinical data on the climatic rhythmicity of the body. Despite the intensification of studies on the climaticity of physiological functions in normal and pathology, many more questions remain poorly studied and unclear (13). A comprehensive analysis of the comparison of anamnestic data with clinical symptoms in SLE in different regions suggests that there is a direct relationship between the primary genetic defect, the features of the clinical picture and the prognosis of the disease. By the end of the 80s of the last century, distribution profiles of various antigens characteristic of representatives of various races and populations were used (7;14). These studies were mainly carried out among the population living in Western Europe and North America. One of the least studied in terms of establishing the antigenic profile of the regions of the world is Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. This is due to the large number of ethnic groups inhabiting its territory. The investigations of O.Nired (1997), Zonana-Nacach (2000) indicate that there's no SLE in Africa. There are contradictions in the works of Z. Amoura (1999), conducted in Paris for 10 years. The author examined 710 patients, among whom 20 patients were residents of Africa, which is 2.9%. Their disease began in Africa. The clinic of the disease in Africans differs from the clinic of the disease in the French (9; 13). Africans had fewer skin manifestations and the phenomenon of "butterfly," but anemic syndrome, Verlhof syndrome, was more common. Anemia was sickle-typed with a hemolytic component (8;14). According to W.Fessel (1974), the frequency of SLE in Chinese living in San Francisco is the same as the white race population, but significantly higher than that of residents living in China. The frequency of SLE in Indians living in the UK is higher than among Indians living in India (Malavija, 1993). Georgian SLE developed much later - at the age of 35-40 years, much more often (5 times) occurred in women, had an acute or sustained course. In Russians, the disease developed much earlier - at the age of 15-20, men and women were affected by the same frequency, the disease more often had a chronic course. Skin damage, photosensitization, enanthema, serositis, neurological disorders, hematological disorders, Raynaud's syndrome was more common in Russians than in Georgians. On the contrary, Georgians were more likely to have fever and kidney damage (10;13).

Conclusions. Thus, the correct assessment of the clinical manifestations of each patient, the search for prognostic markers, as well as the study of the ethnic characteristics of SLE is of great importance both in terms of the prognosis and treatment of the disease, because each form and course of SLE has its own climatic and geographical characteristics. A competent approach to monitoring patients will help develop ways to adequately treat SLE depending on the clinical, immunological features of the disease and the available risk factors for patients living in different regions.

References:

1. Alekberova Z.S., Nasonova V.A., Reshetnyak T.M., Tsitlanadze V.G., Kalandadze N. //Features of systemic lupus erythematosus in Russians and Georgians. Scientific and practical rheumatology. No. 2, 2001, p. 18-22.
2. Demin A.A., Sentyakova T.N. Synchronizing therapy with plasmapheresis and cyclophosphamide of rapidly progressing systemic lupus erythematosus with kidney involvement. // Ter.arch., 1996, No. 5, 27-30.
3. Ivanova M.M., Soloviev S.K. Achievements and new approaches to the treatment of SLE. Scientific and practical rheumatology. No. 2, 2009, p. 18-22.
4. Ilyina A.E. Cardiovascular pathology in systemic lupus erythematosus in men. Dissertation... k. m. N. Moscow, 2009 159 p.

5. Kalandadze N.G. Early diagnosis, peculiarities of treatment and clinical examination of SLE patients., 1998
6. Kotovskaya M.A., Nasonov E.L. Role of anti-nucleosomal antibodies in SLE. Scientific and practical rheumatology. No. 4, 2006, p. 80-85.
7. Lila V.A., Mazurov V.I., Lila A.M. "Incomplete" systemic lupus erythematosus in real clinical practice: diagnostic difficulties. Journal "Therapy" No. 2. Moscow., 2022.
8. Ospanova S.N. Analysis of SLE clinical polymorphism in the Semipalatinsk region. SB RAMS Bulletin. №1 (107). Page 94-96.
9. Rasulov U.R. Features of the clinical course of diffuse connective tissue diseases in the conditions of Tajikistan. Autoreferat diss. cand. honey. sciences. M., 1999
10. Hassan Mohildane Abdel Marouf. Investigation of mechanisms of regulation of peripheral blood leukocyte apoptosis in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. dissertation... Candidate of Biological Sciences, Moscow. 2009. 162 p.
11. Bertsias G., Salmon J., Boumpas D. Therapeutic opportunitites in systemic lupus erythematosus: state of the art and prospects for the new decade. Ann Rheum Dis 2010; 69:1603-11.
12. Calvo-Alen J., Bastian H., Straaton K. et al. Identification of patient subsets among those presumptively diagnosed with, referred, and/or followed up for systemic lupus erythematosus at the large tertiary care center. Arthr Rheum 1995; 38:1475-84."
13. Crowson A.N., Magro C. The cutaneous pathology of lupus erythematosus: a review. J Cutaneous Pathol 2001; 28:1-23.
14. Fernandez A., Quintana G., Matteson E.L. et al. Lupus arthropathy: Historical evolution from deforming arthritis to rhupus. Clin Rheumatol 2004; 23:523-6.
15. Garton M.J., Isenberg D.A. Clinical features of lupus myositis versus idiopathic myositis: A review of 30 cases. Br J Rheum 1997; 36:1067-74.

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